

Original Research

Analysis of Smallholder Farmers Contributions to the Beef Value Chain in Two Zimbabwean Localities (Gokwe South and Mount Darwin)

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ABSTRACT

Zimbabwe has been undergoing a shift, aided by land agricultural reforms and changes in land ownership. As a result, smallholder farmers now dominate the beef value chain. A survey was carried out to analyze smallholder farmers' contributions to the beef value chain in two Zimbabwean areas, Gokwe South and Mount Darwin districts. A multi-stage sampling approach was used to randomly select (n=100) households as respondents. Data was imported and analyzed using SPSS. Chi-square (χ^2) was used to determine the relationship between relevant variables. Results showed that men controlled the beef industry with 69% males against 31% females. The most common ailment was tickborne disease, accounting for 84% of cases in both districts. 95% of respondents relied on their own knowledge to identify diseases. All the farmers relied entirely on natural grazing. About 82% depend on personal savings to fund beef activities, while 69% were unable to obtain loans due to a lack of collateral. There was no significant ($p > 0.05$) relationship the variables considered. Despite the constraints (in disease identification, limited use of other feed alternatives, and personal funds to finance the sector), farmers are encouraged to get more involved in rangeland management and explore new opportunities to get financial access.

Keywords: Feeding systems; Natural grazing; Disease identification; Personal savings; Smallholder farmers

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture has immense potential to stimulate economic growth and improve the livelihoods of smallholder beef farmers. Agriculture contributes between 15 and 18% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (World Bank, 2019). The cattle population is estimated at 5.5 million herds, while the goat stock is 4.7 million (FAO, 2020). In Zimbabwe smallholders own 90% of

the national cattle herd and 97% of the goat stock (Ndlovu et al., 2020; Tavirimirwa et al., 2013). This substantiates the notion of smallholder farmers as the major contributor to the beef value chain and agriculture in supporting Zimbabwe's economy and the livelihoods of the bulk of the population, which resides in rural areas. The Zimbabwean beef sector has been going through transformation since the 2000 land

reform process, with significant ownership, use, and management shifts from a largely commercial farmer-led sector (consisting of 80% commercial farmers) with over US\$50 million in beef exports annually (UNDP, 2019). The transformation resulted in communal farmers being the major participants in the beef value chain (BVC). Among other related rural economic activities, livestock systems represent a potential pathway out of poverty for many smallholders in Zimbabwe (Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2020). Smallholder farmers derive several benefits from cattle in the form of draught power, manure, milk, and wealth status. The benefits have been short-lived as smallholder beef farmers encounter various constraints in production. In Zimbabwe, tick-borne diseases are a major cause of cattle deaths, with a mortality rate of 4.2% (Bennett *et al.*, 2018). High incidences of diseases and mortality rates, and feed shortages lead to low livestock productivity (Masikati, 2010). Results of average losses due to cattle diseases amounted to US\$ 1 288.87 per farmer, with a maximum loss of US\$ 3 660 being recorded during the two years (2020-2021) (Ruzhani and Jambo, 2023).

This has depleted the national herd, and the sector is not socially and economically sustainable for smallholder farmers. Capital is limited, and inputs to improve production are expensive, beyond the reach of many farmers. This has led to several households becoming impoverished. The government initiative, through the Presidential Pasture Production Input Scheme, to over 100,000 cattle farmers significantly increased fodder production and reduced mortalities among smallholder farmers. The efforts were hampered by several constraints, mainly recurring disease prevalence (especially January disease), shortage of rangeland to support production in the winter season, and lack of inputs to enhance regular dipping and deworming of internal and external parasites.

Although it is acknowledged that small-scale farmers encounter several constraints in the livestock sector, to date, there have been a limited number of studies exploring these drawbacks. For instance, Mutibvu *et al.* (2012) observed that diseases, feed, and water were the major limiting factors to the growth of livestock production. In another study, Dube *et al.* (2021)

focused on upgrading the herd through genetic improvement using genomic information incorporated with phenotypic information to derive genomic estimated breeding value (GEBV) as a key constraint to beef production in the country. Despite these studies, there is still a gap in knowledge regarding the commercialization of smallholder farmers into the beef value chain (BVC) in Zimbabwe. This knowledge is critical, not only in resuscitating the beef industry but also in broadening smallholder farmers' contribution to the beef value chain through identifying opportunities in the sector. Therefore, the objectives of this study were to assess the constraints and opportunities for smallholder farmers in the Beef Value Chain (BVC) in Zimbabwe.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

The study was carried out from October 2020 to May 2021 in two districts: Mount Darwin and Gokwe. Mount Darwin District in Mashonaland Central Province is 160 kilometers northeast of Harare, with coordinates of Latitude 16 47' and Longitude 31 35' (Kanyepi and Tanyanyiwa, 2014). Gokwe South District is located in Midlands Province in Zimbabwe's southwest, 225 kilometers from Harare, in latitudes 28°-29° and longitudes 18°-19°.

The two districts have normal rainfall patterns ranging from 450 to 650 mm. The annual temperature in Gokwe South is 23.6°, with October being the hottest month and July being the coldest (Mahakata *et al.*, 2021), but the minimum and maximum temperatures on Mt. Darwin are 18 and 32°C, respectively. Beef farmers in two areas use an extensive production method based on rains from October to February, with abundant vegetation followed by scarcity of vegetation during the dry season (July-September).

Soils in the two districts vary greatly, ranging from sandy, loamy sandy, sandy clay loams, and clay. Because of their semi-arid climate, these places are ideal for animal production. Mixed livestock-crop production systems also boost animal production by reusing crop wastes and arable land during the off-season.

Sampling procedure

To better understand the constraints and opportunities that prevail in the beef value chain in the two districts, the areas were first stratified by agro-ecological regions. Gokwe and Mount Darwin were selected based on the presence of beef farmers. Wards were then randomly selected from the two districts, Mount Darwin with three wards and Gokwe South with two, respectively, followed by purposeful sampling of the villages considering beef farmers only with a minimum herd size of five. 100 samples were collected, resulting in n=50 from Gokwe and n=50 from Mount Darwin, respectively. The sampling was carried out at the household level, taking into account the participants' accessibility and agreement.

Data collection

A structured questionnaire was developed and pretested to ensure its effectiveness by ten trained enumerators. The structured questionnaire was uploaded into KoBoCollect (a mobile data collection software) and administered to the selected study sample. The data collecting tool (Kobo Collect) is a mobile application that collects data in real time and ensures regular viewing progress, consistency, and instant evaluation of descriptive statistics.

Data collected comprised biodata, health management of livestock, supporting infrastructure, access to loans, and supplement feed. To combine quantitative data and correlate with observed patterns, focus group discussions (FGDs) were performed using a checklist, as well as key informant interviews (KII) with extension workers, private players, and NGOs.

DATA ANALYSIS

Descriptive data was initially cleaned, coded, and analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 23. The chi-square (χ^2) test was used to determine the association between variables, namely, gender and disease identification, marital status and loan access, age and disease identification, and educational level and loan access, respectively. Table and figures were used to illustrate our results.

RESULTS

Biography of respondents

Out of the 100 respondents, 69% were males and 31% females. The 36-50 age group had the highest percentage (49%), while the elderly over 65 had the lowest (5%). The majority of the respondents were married (75%), followed by widowed (13%); divorced and single were the least (6% each). In both districts, the majority of farmers were literate; 55% of respondents completed secondary education, followed by 30% who completed basic education; 9% went on to tertiary education, and 6% had no education (**Table 1**). The chi-square revealed no significant ($p > 0.05$) relationship between the studied characteristics.

Table 1: Demographic association of variables with education, loan and access

Variables	Modalities	District		Total	Percentage	Chi Square	p-value
		Gokwe South	Mount Darwin				
Gender and loan access relationship	Male	30	39	69	69	10.58	0.10
	Female	20	11	31	31		
Marital status and disease identification relationship	Single	5	1	6	6	2.92	0.81
	Divorced	3	3	6	6		
	Married	35	40	75	75		
	Widowed	7	6	13	13		
Age and loan access relationship	18-35	23	5	28	28	5.71	0.12
	36-50	21	28	49	49		
	51-65	5	13	18	18		
	65+	1	4	5	5		
Educational level and disease identification relationship	Primary	16	14	30	30	0.21	0.88
	Secondary	28	27	55	55		
	Tertiary	4	5	9	9		
	None	2	4	6	6		

Common diseases

Several diseases were identified as problematic in both districts. Tickborne diseases (84%) are the most common, particularly in Mount Darwin (47%); Gokwe South was the hardest hit by black leg (20%). In the same area, lump skin illnesses (18%) were the most common concern (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Common diseases experienced by farmers in Gokwe South and Mt Darwin districts

Disease identification and treatments

The majority of responders (95%), used their own knowledge to detect diseases, whereas 5% relied on veterinarians and extension agents (Table 2).

Table 2: Disease identification

Age (years)	Disease identification (%)	
	Own knowledge	Veterinary and Extension officer
18-35	25	3
36-50	48	1
51-65	18	0
65+	4	1
Total	95	5

Vaccination

All farmers indicated that they vaccinated their livestock against tickborne diseases. Only few farmers immunize their livestock against blackleg (9%), lump skin (5%), and foot and mouth disease (2%) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Vaccination use

Feeding Systems

The feeding model determines feed quality, which affects animal growth. The survey revealed that 100% of respondents rely primary on natural veld for grazing, among which 95% supplement natural veld grazing with a combination of rangelands and crop residues (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Feeding Systems used by farmers

Utilization Livestock supporting facilities

Respondents indicated that they had storage facilities (74%), feeding facilities (41%), urea pits (33%), and cattle handling facilities (35%) (Figure 4). Despite many farmers indicating that they derived minimum value from these structures due to financial constraints.

Figure 4: Livestock supporting facilities

Farmers using on -farm resources

Legumes and crop residues were the common feed ingredients used as supplements. Other commonly used materials in supplementing include chicken droppings (15%), browsing legumes (11%), legume forages (3%), and legume grains (1%), which are rarely used (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Farmers using on farm resources

Rangeland management and fodder flow support

The majority of farmers used green technologies, with 79% focusing on nutrient recycling through crop residue use (Figure 6). Respondents also said they practiced grazing management (98%), which was common on Mount Darwin. Soil-improving crops were also widely used (67% in both regions). However, soil and water conservation (28%), fodder gardens (17%), and rangeland management had not yet reached maximum capacity. Other approaches, including as herd improvement (3%), pen fattening (2%), and renewable energy (1%), were rarely used (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Use of practices to protect the environment

Table 3 shows the source of finance for respondents (82%) using their personal funds as the sole source of finance in both districts, while 13% relied on savings, and Gokwe South had 5% of respondents funding their projects through remittances.

Table 3: Sources of finance

Source of funds	District		Total
	Gokwe South	Mount Darwin	
Personal funds	39	43	82
Savings	6	7	13
Remittances	5	0	5
Total	50	50	100

Among respondents, the most common reasons for loan denial were a lack of collateral security (69%), ignorance (11%), high interest rates (9%), high exchange rates (9%), and insufficient documentation (2%) (Table 4).

Table 4: Farmers' reasons for not getting loans

Reasons	Percentages (%)
Collateral security	69
Ignorance	11
Exchange rate	9
High interest	9
Inadequate documentation	2
Total	100

DISCUSSION

Results demonstrate that cattle ownership was dominated by males, reflecting the patriarchal nature of the society. These results are consistent with Mapiye's (2009) findings, who observed that households in the rural (84%) and small-scale (95%) areas were male-headed. The patriarchal nature limits the decision-making power of women, as they are often excluded from technical colleges in agriculture and general management of the livestock (FAO, 2017, 2014). In some cultures, women are not allowed to get close to livestock kraals or to make any management decisions regarding animals, as that is considered men's terrain (Mapiye et al., 2018). While women are the backbone

of small-scale agriculture, the farm human resource base, and day-to-day family subsistence input, they face more challenges than men in gaining access to land, inputs, and services. Due to the current situation, beef production is not performing as well as it could because women—who play an important role in agriculture and the rural economy—have less access to productive resources compared to men (Muzari, 2016; FAO, 2011b). The inclusion of females, especially youth, is imperative for livestock improvement programs to ensure sustainability. Fortunately, the problem of education is improving significantly in rural areas (Nkhoru, 2004). This aligns with our results, which showed that youth are slowly acquiring skills in technical colleges, with females starting to stamp their authority in a male-dominated environment. The findings are consistent with Mapiye (2009), who observed that household heads are elderly and the youths are increasingly having access to formal education and are likely to be more productive and more readily accept, initiate, and manage development projects. Access to formal education, especially at the tertiary level, will enhance production in the BVC and promote innovation of new methods.

The results of this study indicate that the majority of the farmers funded their production. This will slow the acceleration of the sector from a communal to a commercial setup. Farmers' unwillingness to dispose of their livestock exacerbates the problem. Maburutse (2012) reported similar findings, stating that rural farmers rarely dispose of cattle because they are viewed as a store of value, a bank, and a symbol of prosperity.

Furthermore, the modest numbers and multiple applications prevent easy disposal. The grading system prejudices smallholder cattle farmers when it comes to pricing indigenous breeds. As a result, farmers' willingness to sell is reduced; they will only sell tired animals after getting value from other uses such as draught power. This demands for a change of the commercial grading system, or, more specifically, the introduction of a grading system for indigenous cattle as an alternative marketing system. This notion has been proposed by Nyamushamba et al. (2017) and Gwiriri et al. (2019).

Respondents heavily relied on their own knowledge in disease identification and vaccination administration; lack of consistent engagement with extension officers and veterinary officers will compromise disease control. Tavimirwa et al. (2013) also concur that the major constraints identified in rural production systems are high disease, parasite prevalence, and low level of disease management. In the current study, tick-borne diseases (TBDs) were found to be the most common disease, causing massive economic losses in Zimbabwean cattle industry.

Government and non-governmental organizations work together to control dipping effectively in the study's locations. However, farmers need to be aware of other diseases that can threaten the herd size. Internal parasites have a substantial impact on livestock growth and the sector's economic viability. These findings are consistent with those reported by Ngongoni et al. (2006), who found that internal parasites have an impact on cattle performance and survival, particularly during the dry season. Tirivanhu et al. (2023) and Masikati (2010) found similar findings, stating that communal herd mortality can be as high as 18% due to disease and parasite incidence, with mortality rates of up to 60% observed in community regions of Masvingo and Manicaland, respectively. Furthermore, improved farmer organization and capacity of extension officers and veterinary officers through government and nongovernment organizations are essential to limit the widespread of diseases and promote consistent vaccination programs (LMAC, 2017).

The results showed that farmers depend on natural rangelands for animal nutrition, mostly a combination of natural pastures and crop residues, and do not use commercial feed except in dire situations to avert deaths. Rangelands offer the cheapest source of feed for the animals, whether on common lands or private lands (Masikati, 2010). Rural farmers rely on subsistence agriculture, own 5-10 cattle, and have limited access to technology and external inputs (Mapiye et al., 2007). As extensive management negatively affects productivity and incomes for their enterprises. Calvers in the lean season risk losing their calves and succumbing to nutritional stress (Ngongoni et al., 2006). Surviving animals must undergo rigorous

compensatory growth in the growing season. This results in unattractive final slaughter weight. Communal cattle also travel for long distances, particularly in the dry season, to find low-quality dry grass or leaves and water. Rural farmers do not regard supplementation with proteins, minerals, and concentrations as an important activity. As a result of resource constraints and the lack of production goals, animals often forage randomly on crop residues in the arable areas after harvesting. There is a need to explore other methods, particularly the production of own farm feeds through fodder crops, the use of cottonseed cakes, veld reinforcements, and the incorporation of high-yielding pasture grasses (Mapiye *et al.*, 2018; Tavimirwa, 2012; Masikati, 2010).

The study findings show that the greater investment in the beef enterprises was largely based on personal sources, such as personal savings and remittances. Many farms have collapsed as a result of farmers' reluctance to acquire financial credit. The government introduced the Agriculture Finance Corporation (AFC) in 2021, but smallholders avoid these loans due to a lack of collateral and the exorbitant interest rates given. Access to loans and utilization of financial services is a significant challenge for smallholders.

Smallholder farmers have diverse needs and backgrounds, varying in their resource base and choice of livestock systems. It is therefore important to understand and categorize target groups, then make subsequent tailor-made products that take into cognizance their priorities and behavior. Incorporation of these actors into the beef value chains will go a long way in bringing sustainability to the sector.

CONCLUSION

The study reveals challenges in disease identification due to overreliance on own knowledge, limited use of other feed alternatives personal expertise, a lack of alternate feed choices, and reliance on personal funds to finance the sector. These constraints can be overcome through regular training and supervision by extension officers. Farmers need to be innovative and utilize on-farm feed ingredients in the formulation of balanced feed to avoid loss of condition during the dry season. All stakeholders involved (government and

non-organizations) need to educate farmers on the importance of financial literacy and encourage the application of loans through insuring their livestock. The financial institutions need to offer affordable loans with low interest to attract farmers.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conception of the study: E.M Methodology and Data collection: EM and GC, Data analysis NC Writing - original draft preparation: EM and GC.

FUNDING

There was no funding for the study.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data set generated and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon request.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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ETHICS APPROVAL

Permission was obtained from the Agricultural and Rural Development Services (ARDS) and community leaders in Mount Darwin and Gokwe South, respectively. Participants were fully informed about the study and given the freedom to decide whether to participate without any coercion.

DECLARATION OF GENERATIVE AI

No AI tools were used in this article

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